

The recalculated (R) and the originally reported values (O.R.V.) of E^0 by (i) Harned and Fitzgerald¹ and Bates² are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—(GENEVA CONVENTION)

Temp. (°C)	E^0_{cell} (O.R.V.)	E^0_{cell} (R)	E^0 of Cd_xHg_y/Cd^{2+} in abs. m _v .	
			Coll (C ₁)	
			(O.R.V.)	(R)
5	580.39	580.20	346.5	346.3
15	577.55	577.40	349.1	348.9
25	573.90	573.90	351.5	351.5
35	569.55	569.53	353.9	353.9
Cell (C ₂)				
5	425.0	426.3	345.1	346.6
15	424.3	424.9	348.3	349.2
25	422.7	423.0	351.4	351.7
35	420.1	420.3	354.1	354.3

The recalculated values of E^0 of Cd_xHg_y/Cd^{2+} electrode from cells (C₁) and (C₂) comes within 0.4 mv. The mean of the recalculated values in volt may be represented by the equation, $-E^0_t = 0.3516 + 2.51 \times 10^{-4}(t-25) - 2.0 \times 10^{-7}(t-25)^2 \dots$ (10)

It may be mentioned that the difference in the values of E^0 reported by (i) Harned and Fitzgerald¹ and (ii) Bates² was due to wrong value of dissociation constant of $CdBr^+$ used by Bates².

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the research grant and for the award of Fellowship to one of them (B.K.C.) and to the authorities of Patna University for library and laboratory facilities.

References

1. H. S. HARNED and M. E. FITZGERALD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 2624.
2. R. G. BATES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 308.
3. G. SAHU and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 233.
4. H. K. SINHA and B. PRASAD, Ph.D. Thesis, Patna University, 1970.
5. H. S. HARNED and R. W. EHLERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 1350.
6. H. K. SINHA and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 901.

Preparation and Properties of some Mesoionic 1,4-Diphenyl-5-Aryltriazole-2-Thiones

P. B. TALUKDAR, S. K. SENGUPTA & A. K. DATTA

Research and Development Division,
East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd., Calcutta-61

Manuscript received 14 April 1972; accepted 4 December 1972

INFORMATION on the derivatives of mesoionic s-triazoles(I)^{1,2} are rather limited, and in this context our efforts to synthesise I from mesoionic thiadiazole (II) were not uniformly successful³.

However, the desired compounds (I) were ultimately obtained in good yield only through a minor modification of a reported procedure² involving treatment of appropriate 1,4-diarylthiosemicarbazide with an aryl chloride. Thus, a series of hitherto unreported compounds (I) were synthesized and their properties are noted in table 1.

All the compounds (I) showed the characteristic λ_{max} in the long wavelength region and the assigned structure was also consistent with the presence of C-S band⁴ around 1340 cm^{-1} . However, data on λ_{max} suggest that an electron withdrawing substituent at C-5 conjugates more effectively with the mesoionic ring than the same substituent at N-1 position. It is interesting to recall that an aryl substituent at C-4 in sydnone exhibit a similar trend when compared with the same substituent at C-5^{5,6}.

Experimental

M.ps are uncorrected (open capillary). Spectral data were obtained with Hilger Recording Spectrophotometer.

Preparation of mesoionic 1,4-diphenyl-5-aryltriazole-2-thiones (I):

1,4-Diphenylthiosemicarbazide (0.5 g) was added to a solution of an aryl chloride (prepared from 0.5 g of acid) in dry benzene (5 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hr on a steam bath. The clear solution usually deposited yellow material during the course of reflux. The mixture was cooled, the precipitated solid was collected and washed with dry benzene. In the absence of any solid, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the operation was repeated twice with addition of fresh benzene.

The crude product, at any event, was treated with a solution (10 ml) of sodium ethoxide (from ca 250 mg of Na) at room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ$). The mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature and then cooled in an ice-bath. The precipitated solid was collected, washed with ethanol and then dried. Crystallisation from ethanol (charcoal) afforded the desired compounds as shown in table 1.

1-p-Bromophenyl-4,5-diphenyl derivative (no. 9, table 1) was synthesized by using the appropriate thiosemicarbazide and benzoyl chloride. Properties of this compound were analogous to other members of the series, although it was not possible to synthesize it from II as reported earlier.³

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF MESOIONIC TRIAZOLES(I)

Compd. Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	λ_{max} (MeOH) $m\mu$ ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$)	Mol. Formula	% S	
					Calc.	Found
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ Ph	310–11	80	320 (3.60); 246 (26.41); 223 (21.44)	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	9.33	9.30
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OPh	274–75 dec	83	316 (5.12); 252 (23.80); 223 (24.21)	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	8.91	8.78
<i>p</i> -BrPh	308–09 dec	73	325 (3.24); 245.5(29.54); 214.5(25.32)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ S	7.84	7.65
<i>p</i> -I-Ph	293–94 dec	82	326 (5.31); 254 (31.09); 214.5(28.81)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ IN ₃ S	7.03	7.40
<i>p</i> -CNPh	335–36 dec	70	350 (3.99); 245.5(33.51); 217 (22.41)	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	9.01	8.78
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -Ph	300–01 dec	53	375 (3.54); 252 (28.30); 215.5(22.99)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	8.56	8.23
<i>m</i> -ClPh	290	55	325 (3.08); 242 (24.67); 220 (25.77)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ S	8.80	8.90
<i>m</i> -EtOPh	252–53	81	~300 (3.69)br; ~244 Sh 228 (26.20)	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	8.57	8.40
Ph and N-1 Ph = <i>p</i> -BrPh	318–19 dec	55	320 (2.86); 230–250 (broad band)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ S	7.84	7.60

References

- M. OHTA and H. KATO in *Nonbenzenoid Aromatics*, Ed. by J. P. Snyder, Academic Press, New York, N.Y., 1969, p. 115.
- K. T. POTTS, S. K. ROY and D. P. JONES, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, **32**, 2245.
- P. B. TALUKDAR, S. K. SENGUPTA and A. K. DATTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 1417.
- M. OHTA, H. KATO and T. KANEKO, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1967, **40**, 578.
- F. H. C. STEWART, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 129.
- C. V. GRECO, J. TOBIAS and L. B. KIER, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1957, **4**, 160.

Mass Spectrometric Identification of Hydrazones of an Aromatic Aldehyde*

S. K. BHASIN & D. N. SEN

National Chemical Laboratory, Poona 8

Manuscript received 22 April 1970; revised 10 February 1972;
accepted

THE mass spectral fragmentation of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones,^{1,2} sulphonyhydrazones,³ N,N-dimethylhydrazones⁴ and some phenylhydrazones⁵ of aromatic aldehydes and ketones have been reported in literature. We became interested in the behaviour under electron impact of salicylaldehyde hydrazone and salicylaldehyde salicyloyl hydrazide—the two ligands used by us⁶ in the course of our

studies on metal chelates. The various ion peaks recorded in the mass spectra of these are given in tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—RELATIVE INTENSITIES OF FRAGMENTS FROM SALICYLALDEHYDE HYDRAZONE

m/e	Intensity %	m/e	Intensity %
136*	100.0	91	25.8
120	23.3	80	7.4
119	28.3	77	12.5
107	16.6	65	8.3

* molecular ion.

TABLE 2—RELATIVE INTENSITIES OF FRAGMENTS FROM SALICYLALDEHYDE SALICYLOYL HYDRAZIDE

m/e	Intensity %	m/e	Intensity %
256*	23.6	107	2.1
137	2.2	93	11.4
136	14.5	92	5.1
135	29.7	80	1.9
121	100.0	77	7.0
120	32.0	65	24.4
119	6.6	—	—

* molecular ion.

It was observed by Das *et al.*⁵ that straight cleavage of N-N bond is the most characteristic fragmentation mode of phenylhydrazones. This feature was also

* N.C.L. Communication No. 1449.